

Research article

Exploring the Japanese dialect geography dialectometrically: Division and continuity

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Abstract: In this paper we explore the Japanese dialect by applying PMI Levenshtein distance to 2400 localities and 37 items of the Linguistic Atlas of Japan Database (LAJDB). Ward's clustering and t-distributed stochastic neighbor embedding (t-SNE) were applied to the average Levenshtein distances among the 2400 localities. Using these techniques we obtained an area map which divides the dialect landscape in areas, and a RGB map that visualized the dialect landscape as a dialect continuum. On the basis of this huge data set we are able to generate very detailed results. Using this methodology we do not need to make subjective choices but provide objective results. We found five optimal groups representing the Tohoku dialects, Eastern dialect, Western dialect, Kyushu dialect and Ryukyuan dialect. We especially focused on the the Ryukyuan varieties and found a division in three groups: Amami dialects, Okinawan dialects and Southern Ryukyuan dialects. Both on the global level and on a more detailed level the results mainly confirmed results from earlier studies.*

Keywords: dialectometry; Japanese dialects; Japanese dialectology; dialect classification; dialect areas

1. Introduction

A “dialect landscape”¹ refers to the geographical distribution and variation of dialects within a particular region. There are several reasons why people may want to visualize the dialect landscape. First, visualizing this diversity helps linguists, researchers, and the general public understand the linguistic richness of their area. Second, visualizations of dialect landscapes can reveal historical migrations, internal culture divisions, trade routes, and interactions that have shaped linguistic variation. Third, governments and educational institutions may use dialect visualizations to make

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¹ In this paper the term 'dialect landscape' refers to the distribution and variation of dialects or regional language varieties within a particular geographic area. We use the term in the same way as Grosse (1955) used the term 'Sprachlandschaft' and Ivić (1962) used the term 'linguistic landscape'.

informed decisions about language policy, curriculum development, and language education. Fourth, knowledge of the dialect landscape may help broadcasters to tailor their broadcasts more precisely to their audience.

For a long time the primary tool for revealing dialect areas within the dialect landscape was the isogloss. An isogloss is a line on a map dividing areas whose dialects differ in some specific respect (Matthews 1997). Using the isogloss method, isoglosses of different phenomena are drawn on a map. Isogloss bundles represent dialect boundaries. See also Inoue (1996, pp. 72–74).

However, isoglosses do not always coincide, but may run parallel or may cross each other; by selecting only coinciding isoglosses the method becomes subjective. A problem mentioned by Kessler (1995) is that isoglosses do not neatly bisect the language area. Often variants do not neatly line up on two sides of a line, but are intermixed to some degree. Another problem which Kessler pointed out is the fact that in case of a dialect continuum with very gradual changes, it seems arbitrary to draw major dialect boundaries between two villages with very similar speech patterns.

The problems that are identified with the isogloss method are eliminated when we use so-called dialectometric methods. Dialectometry means literally ‘the measure of dialect’. This term was coined by Jean Séguy (Chambers & Trudgill 1998: p. 137). He and his associates published the *Atlas linguistique de la Gascogne* that consists of six atlas volumes (Séguy 1973). In these volumes maps are included in which single answers were plotted (Chambers & Trudgill 1998: p. 137). However, Séguy looked for a way to analyze the maps in a more objective way than was possible with traditional analytic methods. For each pair of contiguous sites Séguy and his research team counted “the number of items on which the neighbors disagreed.” The number of disagreements between two neighbors was expressed as a percentage, “and the percentage was treated as an index score indicating the linguistic distance between any two places” (Chambers & Trudgill 1998: p. 138).

The work of Hans Goebel and Edgar Haimlerl is strongly related to the work of Séguy, although independently developed. Instead of distance they measure similarity between two dialects, calculated as the number of items on which two dialects agree, expressed in a percentage (Goebel 1982). They refer to their measure as Relative Identity Value (RIV) (Goebel 2006; 2010).

Similar to Goebel, Kumagai (2016) measured similarity between Japanese dialects using data from the Linguistic Atlas of Japan Database (LAJDB). He calls this measure NC and describes this as the “number of common linguistic features.”

Although the methodology of Séguy, Goebel and Kumagai can be applied to any linguistic level, it is complicated to apply this directly to phonetic transcriptions. After all, several dialect atlases such as the Linguistic Atlas of Japan provide phonetic

transcriptions. A solution was introduced by Kessler in 1995. He measured linguistic distances among Irish Gaelic dialects using Levenshtein distance. The basic idea of this algorithm is that it calculates the cost of changing one string of characters into another. The algorithm was introduced by Vladimir Levenshtein in 1965.

The Levenshtein distance was applied by Huisman et al. (2019) and Huisman (2021) to Japanese dialects, using a newly compiled “comparative dataset based on the 100-item Swadesh List” (Swadesh, 1952). This list includes basic concepts, such as body parts and everyday actions.

In this paper, we research the Japanese dialect landscape using the best of both worlds. Like Kumagai we use the LAJDB, a large data set that includes 2400 locations in Japan, and like Huisman et al. (2019) and Huisman (2021) we will use the Levenshtein distance, supplemented by statistical techniques like cluster analysis and multidimensional scaling. To the best of our knowledge, Levenshtein distance has never been applied to the LAJDB before. While Huisman et al. (2019) and Huisman (2021) used classical Levenshtein distance, we follow Wieling et al. (2009) and Wieling (2012) by using PMI Levenshtein distance.

Additionally, we will especially focus on the Okinawa prefecture which includes the islands southwest of the mainland Japanese area. It consists of several hundred islands that stretch over a distance of 1200 kilometers between Kyushu and Taiwan.

Our paper is structured as follows. In Section 2 we describe the LAJDB, the Levenshtein distance and several statistical techniques for visualizing the dialectal variation. In Section 3 we apply the methodology to Japanese dialects. First, we present the results from all over Japan, and then we zoom in on the Ryukyuan languages. We end with discussion and conclusions in Section 4.

For measuring Levenshtein distances and visualizing the measurements we use LED-A throughout this paper. LED-A is an online web application for calculating linguistic distances with Levenshtein distance and visualizing them. The app is freely available at <https://www.led-a.org>.

2. Methods

2.1. Data source

The description of the data source in this section is based on Kawaguchi & Inoue (2002), Onishi (2002) and Kumagai (2016).

The Linguistic Atlas of Japan (LAJ) is based on a survey that was conducted from 1957 to 1965 by the National Language Research Institute (NLRI) which was the predecessor of today’s National Institute for Japanese Language and Linguistics (NINJAL). 2400 localities were surveyed, and 285 - mainly lexical - items per locality.

The items include nouns, verbs and adjectives. Usually “one male informant (speaker) born before 1903 and born at the given location (or, at least, who spent time there without interruption from the age of 3 to 15) was chosen as informant.” (Kumagai 2016, p. 335)

The LAJ was published from 1966 to 1974 in six volumes (Kokuritsu Kokugo Kenkyujo (NLRI) 1966–1974).

In 1999 professor Yasuo Kumagai and his research team began constructing the LAJDB (Kumagai 2013a, 2013b). The LAJDB includes both the original survey card images and the geographical distribution data of word forms. The linguistic forms shown on the maps of the LAJ are the result of the editor’s classifications of varieties recorded by the fieldworkers.

Kumagai (2016) wrote that “currently, 119 items have been completed, corresponding to 43% of the number of surveyed items (285 items).” We use data from the LAJDB which was available at:

https://www.lajdb.org/lajdb_data/LAJDB_data_withCord_download002_v20180328_rev.html. On this site, data is found for 38 items numbered as 005, 006, 007, 012, 031, 032, 036, 047, 048, 051, 052, 063, 068, 076, 081, 104, 105, 110, 111, 118, 127, 188, 190, 191, 192, 194, 195, 231, 233, 235, 237, 240, 241, 250, 264, 268, 280, and 284.

For each of the items an Excel table is provided. For our analysis we used the column 語形 ‘word form’. The transcriptions in that column represent word forms that may either lexically or phonemically vary, except for item 280 that presumably represents tonemic variation and which we excluded so that 37 items remained. The transcriptions are written in original type of Roma-ji. We made the following adaptations:

- when multiple variants were given like CINNYA(N) they were split like CINNYA / CINNYAN;
- spaces were removed;
- the following characters and character sequences were removed: =, その他, [g], [N*], +, -, ', _, [A@] ;
- in item 081 the following character sequence was removed: << 卑称 >>;
- in items 012 and 110 the following character was removed: [;
- in item 111 @ was replaced by ə;
- in item 104 we removed the following character sequences: [ti], [tui], [tsy:], [tshi:], [tshi], [zi], [t0sui], [t0si:], [t0si], [ts0wi:], [ts0wi], [t0wi], [to@:];
- ~ was replaced by / which is a separator between multiple pronunciations.

The items are listed in Table 1. Not all items were recorded in all locations. But for each of the localities transcriptions of at least 25 items are available.² Figure 1 shows the number of locations in which each item was recorded.

² Actually we found 2402 different locations in the item files at https://www.lajdb.org/lajdb_data/LAJDB_data_withCord_download002_v20180328_rev.html. However, we left out locations 3776.83 and 3787.35 since they have transcriptions for only 7 items. Thus 2400 locations remain which is exactly the number of locations mentioned by Kumagai (2016).

Table 1 37 items from the LAJDB

code	Japanese	English
5	かたつむり	snail
6	なめくじ	slug
7	おたまじゃくし	tadpole
12	とかげ	lizard
31	あたま	head
32	つむじ	whirlpool
36	ものもらい	sty
47	くちびる	lips
48	した (舌)	tongue
51	<塩味が>うすい	lightly salty
52	あまい (甘い)	sweet
63	おやゆび	Thumbelina
68	しもやけ (凍傷)	frostbite
76	うろこ	scales
81	おんな (女)	woman
104	おととい	day before yesterday
105	さきおととい	the day before yesterday
110	しあさって	the day after tomorrow
111	やのあさって	Yano (the day after tomorrow)
118	つゆ (梅雨)	Tsuyu (rainy season)
127	こおる (水が凍る)	Kooru (water freezes)
188	さつまいも	sweet potato
190	とうもろこし	corn
191	かぼちゃ	pumpkin
192	すみれ	violet
194	つくし	horsetail
195	すぎな	too much
231	はげる (禿げる)	bald
233	くるぶし (踝)	ankle
235	すてる (捨てる)	throw away
237	おそろしい	scary
240	ひまご (曾孫)	Himago (great-grandson)
241	やしやご (玄孫)	Yashago (great-grandson)
250	<虹が>きれいだ	the rainbow is beautiful
264	かつぐ (材木)	Katsugu (timber)
268	いる (居る)	there is
284	とんぼ	dragonfly

Fig. 1 For each of the 37 items the number of locations where the item has been recorded is given.

2.2. Levenshtein distance

The Levenshtein distance was introduced in dialectology by Kessler (1995) who used this measure for the comparison of Irish Gaelic dialects. Later it was applied to Dutch, Sardinian, Norwegian, American English, German and Bulgarian dialects, and Bantu languages by others. The algorithm calculates the cost of changing one string of characters into another. In our case the characters are phonetic segments. For example, milk is pronounced as [mɛlɐk] in the Dutch dialect of Haarlem and as [mɔlkə] in the Frisian dialect of Grouw. Now we can change the phonetic transcription of the first realization into the other as is shown in Figure 2. The alignment in Figure 2 shows that the realization of the dialect of Haarlem can be changed into the realization of the dialect of Grouw by substituting the [ɛ] by [ɔ], by deleting an [ə] and by inserting an [ə].

						total
Haarlem	m	ɛ	l	ə	k	
Grouw	m	ɔ	l		k	ə
actual cost		1		1		1
maximum cost	1	1	1	1	1	1
normalized cost						3/6

Fig. 2 Alignment of the realizations of milk in the local dialects of Haarlem and Grouw.

Since [mɛlək] can be changed into [mɔlkə] by three operations, the Levenshtein distance is equal to 3. Many different operation sequences map [mɛlək] → [mɔlkə], but the Levenshtein algorithm always gives the cost of the cheapest mapping.

We also calculate the cumulative maximal cost which we will use to normalize distances. The advantage of normalizing Levenshtein distances is that they can be expressed as a percentage. Percentages are more easily interpreted than ‘raw’ Levenshtein distances. Since the maximum cost of each operation is 1 in our example, and the alignment consists of six slots, the cumulative maximal cost is 6. Then the normalized Levenshtein distance is $3/6$ is 0.5. This means that the two realizations of milk in the local dialects of Haarlem and Grouw differ from each other by 50%.

When the weights of the three operations – substitution, deletion, insertion – are the same (as in our example), it may happen that for some word pairs multiple alignments may yield the (same) minimum cost. In that case the Levenshtein distance is normalized by dividing it by the cumulative maximal cost of the longest alignment. The longest alignment has the greatest number of matches and is linguistically most plausible.³

To accord with syllabification in words, the Levenshtein distance should be based on an alignment with plausible matches. In our implementation of the algorithm the basic rule is that a vowel may only match with a vowel, and a consonant only with a consonant. However, the [w] and the [j] may also match with vowels, and the [u] and the [i] may also match with consonants. The schwa may match with a sonorant. This approach was introduced by Bolognesi & Heeringa (2002) – see also Heeringa (2004) – and was coined as VC-sensitive by Wieling et al. (2009).

Kessler (1995) distinguished between the same-word approach where the Levenshtein distance is only used for comparing word forms that are phonetic or phonological variants of each other, i.e., cognates, and the all-word approach where word forms are also compared to each other when they are lexical variants of each other. Since the word forms of an item in the LAJDB can be both phonetic/phonological variants of each other and lexical variants of each other, we use the all-word approach.

Variation among dialects is usually not measured on the basis of a single word, but on the basis of a set of words. When we compare two dialects by comparing n word pairs with Levenshtein distance, we need to calculate the aggregated distance. In Table 2 we show the procedure by means of an example in which the aggregated distance between Grouw and Haarlem is calculated on the basis of six word pairs. In this example the aggregated distance is $2.35/6 = 0.39$ or 39%.

³ When insertions and deletions have a weight that is the half of the weight of a substitution, all possible alignments of a word pair will have the same cumulative maximal cost. In that case any alignment can be chosen.

Table 2 Normalized Levenshtein distances are calculated between Grouw and Haarlem on the basis of six word pairs. The aggregated distance is $2.35/6 = 0.39$ or 39%.

	Grouw	Haarlem	cost	max. cost	norm. cost
work	vʏrk	vɛrək	2	5	0.4
ship	skɪp	sxɪp	1	4	0.25
finger	fɪŋər	vɪŋər	1	5	0.2
wine	vɪn	vɛɪn	1	4	0.25
house	huz	hœys	3	5	0.75
milk	mɔlkə	mɛlək	3	6	0.5
					2.35

As we mentioned in Section 2.1 not all items were recorded in all locations. So when comparing two local dialects on the basis of 37 word pairs, it may happen that for some pairs, for one or both localities a realization is missing. Since the aggregated distance is calculated as the average of the complete word pairs, the effect of missing transcriptions is discounted.

In Section 2.1 we mentioned that multiple realizations may be given per item. We process all of them. When a location has one realization for a particular item, and another location has n realizations, the n realizations are compared to the realization of the first location, and the n Levenshtein distances are averaged. When one location has $n1$ realizations, and the other location has $n2$ realizations, the $n1$ realizations are multiplied $n2$ times, and the $n2$ realizations are multiplied $n1$ times. Subsequently, pairs are formed so that the average Levenshtein distance is minimized. For details about this procedure see Heeringa (2004, pp. 134–135).

In the examples above all operations bear a ‘cost’ of, for instance, 1. When we compare the realization of milk in the dialect of Haarlem with the realization of the same word in the dialect of Grouw, the substitution of the [ɛ] by [ɔ] has a cost of 1, and the substitution of the [ɛ] by [e] would cost the same, since the phonetic affinity between phones is ignored. In this paper we apply a more sensitive approach where gradual distances between segments are used as operation weights. We follow Wieling et al. (2009) and Wieling (2012) who introduced Pointwise Mutual Information (PMI) Levenshtein as a method for comparing dialects.

Using this method dialects are initially compared by using non-gradual weights, as we did in the examples above. Then new weights are found by analyzing the alignments: the more frequently segments co-occur in a slot within an alignment, the smaller the distance weight. These two steps are repeated, where in the first step the weights that were newly calculated in the second step of the previous iteration are used. The two steps are repeated until the weights do not (or hardly) change any more. PMI

refers to the degree of dependence between aligned segments.⁴ In Figure 3 the algorithm is given in pseudocode. Wieling et al. (2009) found that alignments made by PMI Levenshtein distance improved compared to alignments made by ‘classical’ Levenshtein distance.

<p>repeat</p> <p>compare each variety to each variety by using Levenshtein distance; the first time substitution=ins=del=1, later times the weights calculated in the previous iteration are used;</p> <p>find new weights by analyzing the alignments: the more frequently segments co-occur in an alignment, the smaller the distance weight</p> <p>until weights do not change any more</p>
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Fig. 3 Pseudocode of the PMI Levenshtein distance algorithm.

2.3. Measuring consistency

It is important to check whether the number of items in the data set is large enough to extract a reliable signal. A well-known measure of reliability is the Cronbach's α coefficient, which is derived from the inter-item correlation of the items (Cronbach (1951), see also Heeringa (2004, pp. 170–173) for more details). The value of Cronbach's α ranges between zero and one. The higher the value of Cronbach's α the greater the consistency between the items. A widely accepted threshold is 0.70 (Nunnally 1978, Nunnally & Bernstein 1994).

2.4. Visualizing dialect distances

Aggregated Levenshtein distances can be visualized by means of a beam map. Beam maps were introduced by Goebel (1983), see also Inoue (1996), Goebel (2010), and Kumagai (2016). Localities are connected to neighboring localities by a straight line. The darker the line, the smaller the distance. Lighter lines connect more remote dialects. In order to find neighboring localities, Delaunay triangulation was used. A network of triangles is constructed so that the vertices are the locality points and that there is no

⁴ We used LED-A for calculating the PMI Levenshtein distances. The implementation of PMI-Levenshtein in LED-A differs in details from Wieling (2012). It is beyond the scope of this paper to go into this.

other locality point in the circumscribed circle of a triangle. Delaunay triangulation is named after the Russian mathematician Boris Delaunay (Delaunay 1934).

It is also possible to connect each locality with each locality regardless of whether the locations are adjacent to each other, see for example Heeringa et al. (2010), figures 3a and 4a. However, drawing beam maps on the basis of Delaunay triangulation like Goebel (1983) and others did, produces clearer images.

2.5. Finding dialect areas

In order to find areas in the dialect landscape, we use hierarchical agglomerative cluster analysis (HAC). Jain & Dubes (1988, p. 55) define cluster analysis as ‘the process of classifying objects into subsets that have meaning in the context of a particular problem.’ The goal of clustering is to identify the main groups in complex data. Those groups are called clusters. When using hierarchical agglomerative cluster analysis, a hierarchy of clusters is obtained, where each observation starts in its own cluster, and pairs of clusters are merged as one moves up the hierarchy. HAC was introduced by Goebel (1982) in dialectometry, see also Inoue (1996) and Kumagai (2013, 2016).

The general scheme used for the type of cluster analysis we use here is called Johnson’s algorithm. Jain & Dubes (1988) mention that the scheme was suggested by King (1967) and formalized by Johnson (1967). We will demonstrate the algorithm on the basis of Table 3. This table includes aggregated Levenshtein distances among five local dialects in The Netherlands.

Table 3 Aggregated Levenshtein distances among five local dialects in the Netherlands.

	Grouw	Haarlem	Delft	Hattem	Lochem
Grouw	0	41	44	45	46
Haarlem	41	0	16	34	36
Delft	44	16	0	37	38
Hattem	45	34	37	0	20
Lochem	46	36	38	20	0

Since the matrix is symmetrical (for example, the distance between Grouw and Haarlem is the same as between Haarlem and Grouw), we focus only on the values that are shown in bold. We start by looking for the smallest distance in the matrix. The smallest distance is 16, which is found between Haarlem and Delft. Therefore, we consider ‘Haarlem & Delft’ as one cluster. Both Haarlem and Delft are removed from the matrix, and a new cluster Haarlem & Delft is inserted. To iterate, we have to assign a distance from the newly formed cluster to all other points. For example, the distance between Grouw and Haarlem & Delft is calculated as the average of the distance

between Grouw and Haarlem (41) and the distance between Grouw and Delft (44) which is $((41+44)/2=)$ 42.5.

After calculating the distances between Hattem and Haarlem & Delft and between Lochem and Haarlem & Delft as well, we get the distance matrix that is shown in Table 4.

Table 4 Aggregated Levenshtein distances among four local dialects in the Netherlands and the cluster ‘Haarlem & Delft’.

	Grouw	Haarlem & Delft	Hattem	Lochem
Grouw	0	42.5	45	46
Haarlem & Delft	42.5	0	35.5	37
Hattem	45	35.5	0	20
Lochem	46	37	20	0

In each iteration the matrix is reduced in size. The iterations are repeated until no elements are left which can be fused to a new cluster. The final result is a complete hierarchical grouping of varieties. This grouping is visualized as a dendrogram, a tree in which the leaves are the varieties and the lengths of the branches correspond with the distances. In our example we get the dendrogram that is shown in Figure 4.

Fig. 4 Dendrogram obtained on the basis of the distance matrix in Table 2 using hierarchical agglomerative cluster analysis.

In our example the distance of an element –either a local dialect or a cluster– to a newly formed cluster is calculated by averaging. We calculated the average of the distance between Grouw and Haarlem and the distance between Grouw and Delft, thus we obtained the distance between Grouw and the cluster Haarlem & Delft. This type of clustering is known as Unweighted Pair Group Method using Arithmetic averages (UPGMA).

Several alternatives exist as well. In later work of Hans Goebel the Ward’s method was used, see, for example, Goebel (2006, 2007, 2010). This method minimizes the variance in the clusters (Ward, 1963). At each stage those two clusters are found whose merger gives the minimum increase in the total within group error sum of squares.

Gere (2023) extensively validated several cluster methods, including the Ward’s method. He concludes that using the “Ward’s method seems a safe and reasonable

choice.” The dendrograms produced by the Ward’s method have well distributed clusters, i.e. they are “symmetric and seem to have evenly distributed clusters.” As for a division into two groups, the Ward’s method produced clusters that were most significantly different.

The dendrogram provides valuable insight in the relationships among the local dialects. Additionally, we can derive dialect areas from the tree structure, and draw these areas in a map which we call area map.

Areas can be derived from the dendrogram by drawing a vertical line somewhere in the dendrogram and counting the horizontal lines matching it. Local dialects connecting to the matching horizontal lines will then belong to the same cluster (or area).

In order to find the optimal number of clusters, we have to find the right position of that vertical line in the dendrogram. This position is found by looking at the distances between the successive nodes in the dendrogram. In Figure 5 the nodes are numbered from 1 to 4. Each node marks the fuse of elements (local dialects or dialect clusters), and the number indicates the order in which the elements were fused. Then we have to find the largest horizontal difference between two successive nodes. In Figure 5 it can be seen that the largest distance between two successive nodes is between nodes 2 and 3. Now we draw a vertical line in the middle of these two nodes. The result can be seen in Figure 6. The number of horizontal lines that is intersected by that vertical line is the optimal number of clusters. In Figure 6 this vertical line intersects three horizontal lines which connect to three groups, namely Grouw, Delft and Haarlem, and Hattem and Lochem. Therefore, the optimal number of clusters is 3 in our example.⁵

Fig. 5 The dendrogram has four nodes which are numbered from 1 to 4. Each node marks the fuse of elements (local dialects or dialect clusters), and the numbers indicate the order in which the elements were fused.

⁵ For more information about this procedure see <https://statsandr.com/blog/files/Hierarchical-clustering-cheatsheet.pdf>. This procedure is implemented in LED-A.

Fig. 6 The largest distance between two successive nodes is between nodes 2 and 3. A vertical line is drawn in the middle of these two nodes and intersects with three horizontal lines that connect with three groups.

When the dialect areas that are represented by the cluster groups are drawn in a map, each area gets a unique color. The way colors are assigned to the areas is described at the end of Section 2.6.

2.6. Showing the dialect continuum

Multidimensional scaling was introduced in dialectometry by Embleton (1993) (see also Embleton et al. (1993)). By using multidimensional scaling (MDS) we are able to visualize the dialect landscape as a continuum. When applying MDS to our example set of five local Dutch dialects, we obtain the plot shown in Figure 7. In this figure the five local dialects are put on a map so that the distances in two-dimensional space reflect the distances in the matrix as closely as possible. Like dialects are plotted nearby and unlike dialects are plotted distant to each other.

Fig. 7 Using MDS the five dimensions are reduced to two dimensions. X-coordinates represent the first, and Y-coordinates represent the second dimension.

MDS exists in several variants. Togerson (1952) proposed the first metric method, known as classical MDS. Kruskal extended this to non-metric MDS, which uses the ranks of the distances (Kruskal & Wish 1978). The plot shown in Figure 7 is made using Kruskal’s non-metric MDS.

In this paper we use t-Distributed Stochastic Neighbor Embedding (t-SNE) (Van der Maaten and Hinton, 2008; Van der Maaten, 2014). Van der Maaten and Hinton (2008) write that “t-SNE is capable of capturing much of the local structure of the high-dimensional data very well, while also revealing global structure such as the presence of clusters at several scales” and that t-SNE “produces significantly better visualizations by reducing the tendency to crowd points together in the center of the map” which we found a justification for using this method in this paper.

In LED-A the function `Rtsne` of the R package `Rtsne` is used (Krijthe, 2015). This function has a perplexity parameter which is related to the number of nearest neighbors considered when placing each data point. When using lower values more attention is paid to the local aspects of the data, and the use of higher values increases the impact of more distant neighbors and global structure. Van der Maaten and Hinton (2008) write that “typical values are between 5 and 50”. The perplexity value is set to 30 by default. When the number of localities is smaller than 91, this would result in an error message: “Perplexity is too large”. In order to get the perplexity value as close as possible to the default value when the number of localities is smaller than 91, we calculate:

$$\text{perplexity} = (n - 1) \text{ DIV } 3$$

where n is the number of localities.

Using MDS it is possible to scale multidimensional data to two dimensions (like we did in Figure 7) or to three or more dimensions. When scaling to three dimensions, each local dialect is represented by three values, i.e., a value for x , y and z . If we let x be the intensity of red, y the intensity of green and z be the intensity of blue, each dialect gets its unique color. In this way, each dialect point is associated with a mix of colors depending on its coordinates in the three-dimensional MDS solution, and a map is obtained that visualizes the dialect landscape as a continuum. The first MDS color map was published by Nerbonne & Heeringa (1998). Shortly afterwards the same map was also published by Nerbonne et al. (1999). We refer to this kind of maps as RGB maps.

In a RGB map each locality has its unique color. We also assign unique colors to the areas in an area map (see Section 2.5) by averaging the colors of the individual localities within each area.

2.7. Visualizing the dialect landscape from the perspective of a reference point

A reference point map is a map that shows the similarity or difference of local dialects compared to a reference point. The reference point can be one of the local dialects, a supraregional variety, a standard language or the proto-language. Reference point maps were introduced by Goebel (1981), see also Inoue (1996). While the black and white maps published in 1981 use different line patterns in order to express the similarity compared to the reference points, in later publications colors are used. Goebel (2002), for example, uses a rainbow scheme – red, orange, yellow, green, blue –, where dialects most similar to the reference point are red, and most distant dialects are blue. In LED-A a rainbow scheme is used as well. Kumagai (2016) varies the dot size: the larger the dot the more similar a variety is to the reference point.

3. Application to Japanese dialects

In this section we present the results of measuring aggregated normalized PMI Levenshtein distances among 2400 localities on the basis of 37 items from the LAJDB. In Section 3.1 we present the results of Japan, and in Section 3.2 we focus on Ryukyuan languages. We will compare our results to the other maps of Inoue & Yoshioka (2003) (see Map 1a and Map 1b) and to the map of Huisman et al. (2019), p. 8, Figure 1. The latter map is also found in Huisman (2021), p. 68, Figure 3-2.

3.1. Japanese dialects

First the conclusive explanation will be given.

The measurements for the full set of 2400 localities and 37 items appeared to be extremely consistent. We found a Cronbach's α value of 0.9978 which indicates that 37 items are enough to provide a reliable results (see Section 2.3).

The clear correspondence between preceding studies of Japanese dialectologists in Maps 1a and 1b, and our results in Maps 2 to 11 is impressive.

3.1.1. Dialect division theory and concentric distribution theory

An overview of trends in the study of Japanese dialects over the past 100 years reveals a conflict between the dialect division theory (*kukaku-ron*) and concentric distribution theory (center versus periphery theory, *shuken-ron*). Map 1a is a composite of a number of figures, superimposed on each other.

(1) The dialect division theory is concerned with boundaries, which Tojo (1927 and 1953) focused on. The isoglosses of grammar, phonology, pitch accent and lexicon (words) became the basis, and the East-West difference and the positions of Kyushu and Okinawa were the main themes.

(2) Yanagida (1943) proposed a theory of dialectal concentric distribution based on the dialectal names of snail and pointed out the distant agreement between periphery areas. He was not interested in the dialect division. Haruhiko Kindaichi (1955) pointed out the distant agreement mainly on the basis of pitch accent, but it should be called “reverse concentric distribution theory” because it was based on maintenance at the center and modification at the periphery, shown in Map 1a by the density of the brown color of the regions.

(3) Fujiwara (1990) pointed out the continuity of dialects, shown in Map 1a by the pattern and angle of straight and wavy lines in the region.

Map 1a Dialect areas in Japan (Inoue & Yoshioka 2003). The map is supplemented with the numbers of the five clusters, for the sake of comparison with the results of our analysis, since they are almost identical.

1 Tohoku dialect, 2 Eastern dialect, 3 Western dialect, 4 Kyushu dialect, and 5 Ryukyuan dialect (or Ryukyuan language(s), Okinawan dialects).

Map 1b shows the conclusions of Map 1a and Inoue (2001). As in Map 1a, the numbers of the five clusters have been supplemented. (This is in good agreement with the cluster analysis in Map 3 below.)

Map 1b Japanese dialects according to Inoue & Yoshioka (2003).

3.1.2. UNESCO list of languages in danger

Map 1b differs from the eight languages in danger of UNESCO 2009. Dialectologists have diverse opinions about the subdivisions of Ryukyuan languages. Map 1b shows Ryukyuan languages divided into three groups: Amami (5.1), Okinawa (5.2), and Sakishima (5.3), while UNESCO 2009 divided in more detail into six groups as Amami (5.1), Kunigami (5.2), Okinawan (5.2), Miyako (5.3), Yaeyama (5.3) and Yonaguni (5.3). The criteria of UNESCO 2009 are unclear, both in terms of (linguistic) mutual intelligibility and in terms of extra-linguistic factors (former political boundaries). The Hachijo dialect, one of the languages in danger⁶, is placed outside the mainland dialects in Map 1b.

3.1.3. Overview of results of computational analysis

In Map 2a beam map is shown. In the map dark lines represent small distances and light lines large distances. Only adjacent localities are connected by lines (see Section 2.4). The map shows mainland Japan as a large continuum without any clear division

⁶ It is considered to be a lineage of the ancient Eastern dialects.

in groups. In the southwest we find the Ryukyuan languages clearly distinguished from mainland Japan which are in turn distinguished in a northern and southern group.

Map 2 Beam map of 2400 Japanese localities.
Dark lines represent small distances and light lines large distances.

3.1.4. Dendrogram in cluster analysis

We obtain a sharper and more detailed classification by means of Ward's clustering. The dendrogram is shown in Figure 8. The Dendrogram shows the branching process and hierarchy of the cluster analysis. The blue vertical line on the left suggests a division in five groups, which is the optimal number of groups (see Section 2.5). The blue vertical line on the right suggests a more detailed division in 15 groups. The two vertical lines show the reference points on the overall branching process. The five optimal groups are shown in Map 3, and the 15 groups are shown in Map 4.

Fig. 8 Dendrogram.

The dendrogram was obtained by Ward's clustering on the basis of the aggregated normalized Levenshtein distances among 2400 Japanese localities. The blue vertical line on the left suggests a division in five groups, which is the optimal number of groups (see Section 2.5). The blue vertical line on the right suggests a more detailed division in 15 groups.

3.1.5. Map display of cluster analysis

When comparing our Map 3 with Map 1b, we find in both maps the Ryukyuan languages (5), the Kyushu dialects (4), and a Western Japanese group (3). Our Eastern Japanese group (2) includes the Chubu dialects and the Kanto dialects. The group of Tohoku dialects (1) in our map mainly overlaps with Tohoku dialect group. In our map the Hokkaido dialects belong to the Western Japanese group (3), with some exceptions that belong to Eastern Japanese. This is the same as in Map 1b. Note also the green dot south of the Eastern Japanese group (2) which represents a Hachijo variety and which is classified among the Tohoku dialects.

The five clusters in Map 3 are plausible results, easy to understand and consistent with the preceding theory. The clusters are again numbered from north to south. The five clusters are consistent with Map 1b. The five clusters are also bisected into east (1 2) and west (3 4 5) clusters.

However, compared to Figure 8, the order of bifurcation (tree hierarchy) is different. What is different is that Ryukyu (5) and Kyushu (4) do not separate as early as in Figure 8. The boundaries in Map 3 correspond almost exactly to the prefectural boundaries, but there are some enclaves. We will see this in detail later. The study of Inoue (2001) was based on data that were averaged per prefecture, so minute enclaves were not visible. Yarimizu (2007) is the result of a multivariate analysis of the data per locality, and similar enclaves were observed.

In Map 4 a more detailed division into 15 groups is provided. Again Ward's clustering was used. Here we find especially that the further division of the Ryukyuan languages and the Western Japanese group agrees with Map 1a.

Due to the difference in detail, it is more difficult to compare the division of the mainland with the map of Huisman et al. (2019).

Map 3 Clustering of five optimal groups.
Ward's clustering was applied to the average normalized Levenshtein distances among the 2400 Japanese localities. Five optimal groups were found which are shown in this map.

Map 4 Division into 15 groups.
2400 Japanese local dialects into 15 groups. Ward's clustering was applied to the average normalized Levenshtein distances among the localities.

3.1.6. A more detailed discussion of dialect groupings

In this section we discuss the dialect groupings in more detail. We view the groups from the north to the south on Map 4 and check them against the dendrogram in Figure 8.

3.1 Hokkaido dialect

In Figure 8, Hokkaido is a part of Western dialects (3) in the dendrogram, belonging to the same cluster as the subcluster Gifu-Aichi (3.3). This is the only case where there is no geographical continuity on the map. This is because of mass migrations in the settlement frontier since the early modern period⁷.

1 Tohoku dialect

The dendrogram in Figure 8 divides the area into two parts: Northern Tohoku (1.1) and Southern Tohoku (1.2). This is in close agreement with the conventional dichotomy based on pitch accents. In Map 4 Northern Tohoku includes Sado Island.

Southern Tohoku is almost the same as the “no (monotypic) pitch accent region”, but there is a discrepancy with the boundary of Ibaraki and other prefectures (there is an enclave). It differs from the conventional division in that it includes Hachijo Island.

Dialects of remote (peripheral) areas are not prominent here. The pronunciation of Otori in Yamagata Prefecture and Hinoemata in Fukushima Prefecture are different from Tohoku dialectal, but are not prominent in this analysis.

2 Eastern dialect

In this cluster, the Kanto dialect and a large region of Na-Ya-Shi dialect (Nagano, Yamanashi, and Shizuoka prefectures) are grouped together and not separated. However, according to Figure 8, if the vertical line is shifted a little more to the right, the number of clusters becomes 16, and Kanto dialect and Na-Ya-Shi dialect are divided into two clusters of approximately the same size.

In Map 4 this is consistent with the east-west boundary line (Itoigawa-Hamanako line). The important east-west boundary, the North Alps, is exceptional. Blank areas with no inhabited settlements indicate the steepness of the natural terrain.

3 Western dialect

In Figure 8 three Western dialects cover a large area and are subdivided into many regions.

3.1 Hokkaido has already been described.

3.2 Hokuriku dialect

⁷ It reminds us of interpretation of ALF enclaves by Goebel (2010).

Hokuriku includes the Toyama-Ishikawa-Fukui prefectures, which belong to the Western dialects. It is consistent with geography and administrative divisions, but does not include Niigata prefecture, which belongs to the Eastern dialect.

3.3 Gifu Aichi (Gi-A) dialect

This belongs to the west side of the east-west boundary of the Northern Alps. In Map 4, most of the localities in Aichi prefecture fall into the Kanto dialect and Na-Ya-Shi dialects (2.1), while the actual localities are almost exclusively in Gifu Prefecture.

3.4 Kansai dialect

Kansai is a large area of Kinki Region that includes Kyoto and Osaka, which were the center of Japanese cultural transmission in the pre-modern era. Other quantitative analysis shows a high degree of internal homogeneity in the Kansai dialect.

There is an enclave in the southern Kii Peninsula (Wakayama prefecture) which is similar to Gifu-Aichi dialect, and the connection to the enclave in the pitch accent is of interest.

3.5 Chugoku dialect

In Figure 8 there is a stage where Chugoku-Shikoku dialect is separated from the other clusters and is coming together as a cluster.

In Map 4 the Izumo-Inaba dialect (in the Shimane and Tottori prefectures) is not separated. The Northern San-in region is continuous with the southern San-yo region, and the area along the Seto Inland Sea is continuous. Furthermore, there are many enclaves of Kansai dialects in the central part of the Chugoku Mountains.

3.6 Shikoku dialect

In Figure 8 Shikoku is clearly separated from the others. Map 4 shows the distribution of enclaves of the Kansai dialects in Shikoku.

4 *Kyushu dialect*

Kyushu dialects (4) are grouped together. It is consistent with the conventional theory that Kyushu dialect is divided into three parts. However, there are enclaves in the Kyushu cluster.

Honichi dialects (4.1) of Oita and Miyazaki prefectures are located on the east coast of Kyushu, including Tsushima island (belonging to Nagasaki prefecture but with significant influence from Fukuoka prefecture in terms of transportation and economy). There is an enclave in Hiroshima prefecture.

Hichiku dialect (4.2) in Fukuoka, Saga, Nagasaki and Kumamoto prefectures is located on the west coast of Kyushu, with enclaves in the mountainous areas along its boundaries.

Satsugu (Satsuma Osumi) dialect (4.3) extends beyond Kagoshima prefecture in terms of its boundaries into the territory of Kumamoto prefecture.

5 Ryukyuan languages

As for the Ryukyuan languages (5), the Southern Ryukyuan languages in our map are divided in Yaeyama Ryukyuan and Miyako Ryukyuan in the map of Huisman et al. (2019). Both in the map of Huisman et al. (2019) and in our map we find a distinction between the Okinawan language and the Amami language, but the boundary between the two groups is found more to the south in our map, making the groups of Amami varieties larger and the groups of Okinawan languages smaller.

Ryukyuan languages (5) are grouped together and have no enclaves, and the trichotomy into Amami, Okinawan, and Southern Ryukyuan is consistent with the preceding theories. In the dendrogram of Figure 8, Southern Ryukyuan (5.3) is trisected into three sub-divisions. In Map 4 there are no color differences among the three divisions, but they are subdivided in the RGB map of Map 11.

3.1.7. Application of multidimensional scaling

In Map 5 a multidimensional scaling (MDS) plot is shown. Using t-SNE the distances among the 2400 localities were scaled to two dimensions. The colors correspond with the colors in Map 4. The groupings suggested by the plot itself and by the cluster analysis agree relatively well with each other. However, the Northern Tohoku dialects 1 (yellowish green), Southern Tohoku dialects 1 (green) and Kanto and Na-Ya-Shi dialects 2 (lighter blue) which are distinguished by the cluster analysis look more like a continuum in the plot itself.

In Map 5, the five clusters were numbered, and the locations of the regions resemble the east-west configuration of the Japanese archipelago. However, among the three western regions, Hokuriku (3.2) and Gifu-Aichi (3.3) are reversed from north to south.

The graph reflects the geographical arrangement of the three regions in the results of many previous multivariate analyses. This indicates the reliability of the multivariate analysis.

Map 5 Multidimensional scaling plot.

Multidimensional scaling plot obtained on the basis of the average normalized Levenshtein distances among the 2400 Japanese localities. Using t-SNE the distances were scaled to two dimensions. The colors correspond with the colors in Map 4.

3.1.8. Visualizing the continuum in a RGB map

The RGB map in Map 6 shows the Japanese dialect landscape as a continuum. Especially the Ryukyuan varieties 5 and the Kyushu varieties 4 in the most southern part of mainland Japan are well distinguished. In the Western Japanese group 3 a tripartite division in Chugoku 3.5, Shikoku 3.6 and Kansai 3.4 varieties can be recognized. The Hokuriku dialects 3.2 are clearly distinguished within the Western Japanese group 3. Within the group of Tohoku varieties 1 a division between northern varieties 1.1 and southern varieties 1.2 can more or less be recognized.

Continuity

The RGB Map shows the continuity of the various dialects. In conclusion, this map depicts the reality of all dialects in the Japanese archipelago as continuous, as opposed to cluster analysis. In Map 6 R Red is for Kyushu (4), G Green is for Ryukyuan (5), B Blue is for Eastern (2).

Boundaries

The RGB Map should show continuity, but the boundary line is clearly visible. The more southern, the more pronounced, especially between Ryukyu (5) and Kyushu islands (4), and between Kyushu islands (4) and western dialects (3) of Chugoku and Shikoku. The other dialects without ocean border are continuous, as in Chugoku and Kansai dialects (3).

The difference between the east-west boundary of the steep Northern Alps is large at the northern end, Hokuriku, while the Tokaido side at the southern end is continuous.⁸ Eastern (2) and Tohoku (1) also appear to be continuous.

Compared to the Dutch RGB Map, Map 6 shows clear differences in coloration. There is a difference with Swiss German even in the same Germanic languages.

⁸ This phenomenon corresponds to the Rhenish fan in the German dialects.

Map 6 RGB map of all Japan

RGB map obtained on the basis of the average normalized Levenshtein distances among the 2400 Japanese localities. Using t-SNE the distances were scaled to three dimensions. The first dimension is mapped inversely to red, the second inversely to blue and the third inversely to green. Thus each location gets its own unique color and the dialect landscape is visualized as a continuum.

3.1.9. Reference point map with Tokyo as reference point

In Map 7 the Japanese local dialects are compared to the dialect spoken in or close to Tokyo.⁹ Distances are visualized by colors according to a rainbow scheme. Red means that a local dialect is identical to the dialect of location 5698.69, and darker blue means that a local dialect is maximally different from location 5698.69. In general, the greater the geographical distance from Tokyo, the greater the aggregated normalized Levenshtein distance. The most distant local dialects are found in the Ryukyuan group.

There is an older attempt at degrees of agreement with the standard form or Tokyo form using prefecture-by-prefecture averages (Inoue 2001), and there is also an analysis based on the grammatical phenomena of GAJ 800 localities data by Yarimizu (2007). Comparing the data from the standard (map headword form) or Tokyo respondents to each prefecture or each informant is almost proportional to distance. Using the rail distance from the old capital Kyoto and the new capital Edo Tokyo, a link between pre-modern and post-modern transportation routes was ascertained (Inoue 2020). It can be inferred from this map.

⁹ In the LAJDB all localities are represented by codes. We determined location 5698.69 closest to Tokyo just by eyeballing.

Map 7 Reference point map

Reference point map showing the distances of 2399 local Japanese dialects relative to point no. 5698.69 (Tokyo). Distances are visualized by colors according to a rainbow scheme. Red means: local dialect is identical to the dialect of location 5698.69, darker blue means: the local dialect is maximally different from location 5698.69.

3.2. Ryukyuan languages

In this section we focus on the relationship between the various localities inside the Ryukyuan languages.

The LAJDB includes 83 local dialects that belong to the Ryukyuan languages (5, see Map 4). The items with the numbers 194 and 195 were not found for the localities in this area, therefore our measurements are obtained on the basis of 35 items. When calculating the average normalized Levenshtein distances among the localities, we used the PMI segment distances (see Section 2.2) that were calculated on the basis of the complete set of 2400 localities.

We measured Cronbach's α and found a value of 0.9348, which is much higher than the widely accepted threshold of 0.7. Therefore, we can be confident that our results are reliable.

3.2.1. Overview of metrological analysis results

In Map 8 a beam map shows the relationships of adjacent localities to each other. When applying Ward's clustering to the 83 local dialects, the optimal number of clusters (or groups) is three.

The dendrogram is shown in Figure 9 and the area map in Map 9. For the coloring of the groups we used again the procedure that is described at the end of Section 2.6. The dendrogram shows the branching process. In the dendrogram two blue vertical lines are drawn. The one on the left divides into the top three clusters, and the one on the right divides into the top nine clusters. Southern Ryukyuan is conventionally divided into three clusters (also by UNESCO). If a vertical line is drawn at that position, Okinawan is divided into two clusters, and Amami is divided into four clusters, together dividing it into nine clusters.

Map 9 shows the division into the top three clusters on a map. The three clusters are neatly divided geographically. A map showing the division in nine clusters is omitted.

Map 8 Beam map of 83 local dialects that belong to the Ryukyuan languages.
Dark lines represent small distances and light lines large distances.

Fig. 9 Dendrogram

The dendrogram was obtained by Ward's clustering on the basis of the aggregated normalized Levenshtein distances among 83 local dialects that belong to the Ryukyuan languages. The blue vertical line on the left suggests a division in three groups, which is the optimal number of groups (see Section 2.5). The blue vertical line on the right suggests a more detailed division in nine groups.

Map 9 Clustering of three optimal groups.

The 83 local dialects that belong to the Ryukyuan languages divided into three groups. Ward's clustering was applied to the average normalized Levenshtein distances among the localities.

3.2.2. Application of multidimensional scaling

In Map 10 a multidimensional scaling plot can be found. Using t-SNE the distances among the 83 localities were scaled to two dimensions. The colors correspond with the colors in Map 9. The groupings suggested by the plot itself and by the cluster analysis agree relatively well with each other.

The results of application of the MDS were mapped. It is clearly divided into three parts, with an intermediate point between Amami and Okinawa, but no enclaves were observed. This is a major difference between the mainland, which is almost completely connected by land, and the Ryukyu Islands, which have many isolated islands.

Map 10 Multidimensional scaling plot

Multidimensional scaling plot obtained on the basis of the average normalized Levenshtein distances among 83 local dialects that belong to the Ryukyuan languages. Using t-SNE the distances were scaled to two dimensions.

3.2.3. Visualizing the continuum in a RGB map

Map 11 shows the RGB map. The map suggests a division in three groups as well, although some heterogeneity is found within the groups, especially within the groups of the Okinawan dialects.

When looking closer to the beam map in Map 8, the dendrogram in Figure 9 and the multidimensional scaling plot in Map 10, we find two subgroups within the Southern Ryukyuan group 5.3 which correspond with the Yonaguni and Yaeyama dialects in the southwest and the Miyako dialects more to the northeast. In the RGB map, however, the colors of those two subgroups are not strongly distinguished. Rather we find the Yonaguni variety – represented by the most western purple dot – distinguished from the other Southern Ryukyuan varieties.

Map 11 RGB map

The map was obtained on the basis of the average normalized Levenshtein distances among the 83 local dialects that belong to the Ryukyuan languages. Using t-SNE the distances were scaled to three dimensions. The first dimension is mapped inversely to red, the second to green and the third to blue.

The RGB Map shows continuity. In conclusion, the entire area of Ryukyuan dialects is expected as continuous in reverse to the cluster analysis. In Map 11, R Red is for Okinawan (5.2), G Green is for Amami (5.1), and B Blue is for Southern Ryukyuan (5.3). In terms of color, the differences among the three clusters are significant, as shown in Map 9. There is a continuity of tints between Okinawan (5.2) and Amami (5.1), but there is a clear difference between Okinawan (5.2) and Southern Ryukyuan (5.3). Its internal difference is small in terms of tint. This is a trend not observed in the whole Japan scale RGB Map (Map 6).

Since Ryukyuan dialects are internally diverse, 37 items of our data were not sufficient. It is desirable to treat quantitatively with a larger number of items. However, as in Nakamoto (1983, p.166), there are cases in which even a small number of items could show the internal concentric distribution of Ryukyuan dialects in the former Ryukyu Kingdom. The choice of items is also important.

4. Discussions and conclusions

4.1. Direct results

Using the dialectometric methodology as presented in this paper and implemented in LED-A we were able to measure and visualize lexical and phonetic/phonological variation in word forms of 2400 local dialects and 37 items from the LAJDB. By using the dialectometric approach, with PMI Levenshtein distance as our workhorse, we did not suffer from the limitations of the traditional isogloss method, i.e. we could utilize all the information that is contained by the transcriptions without making subjective choices. By using different visualization techniques – beam maps, areas maps, RGB maps and reference point maps – we were able to visualize dialect variation from different but complementary angles and at different levels of detail.

The results that we obtained are plausible and consistent with the preceding studies such as those from Fujiwara (1990), Inoue (2001) and others. They reinforce, rather than contradict, the results of previous Japanese dialectologists. This outcome also confirms the validity, convenience, and reliability of the Levenshtein distance.

In lexicostatistics proposed by M. Swadesh in the 1950s, the question was not whether the word forms were similar but whether they were cognates. The LAJ was concerned with derivational relations between word forms, and the choice of map symbols reflected derivational relations. The GAJ, on the other hand, was interested in the grammatical conjugation system, and sometimes treated words with similar pronunciations as grammatically distinct. Both were based on the researcher's academic knowledge and were virtuoso and subjective. In contrast, the Levenshtein distance is an objective criterion and reliable.

Methodologically speaking, our approach is very similar to Huisman's (2019). As to the differences we note the following:

1. We measured all-word distances which include both lexical and phonetic/phonological variation.

2. Huisman et al. (2019) used 100 items from the Swadesh list which includes basic concepts. Our word list contains some basic concepts as well, but also less basic concepts like *tadpole*, *dragonfly* and *whirlpool*. The difference in concepts may explain the difference in results. Huisman et al. (2019) may have measured all-word distances as well, but they do not mention this explicitly.

3. We do not expect that the difference in the number of items (100 versus 37) plays a role. We found Cronbach's α values larger than 0.9 which shows that our measurements are very reliable (see Section 2.3, 3.1 and 3.2).

4. Huisman et al. (2019) used ‘classical’ Levenshtein distance, whereas we used PMI Levenshtein distance, which may also explain the difference between their and our results.

5. The analysis of Huisman et al. (2019) is obtained on the basis of 58 Japanese and 32 Ryukyuan varieties. The LAJDB includes 2317 Japanese and 83 Ryukyuan varieties. This allowed us to zoom in more deeply on the results (see, for example, Maps 4 and 5).

6. Like Huisman et al. (2019) we applied Ward’s clustering to the Levenshtein distance matrix. However, in addition to this we used t-SNE for plotting dialect relationships in two-dimensional space and for creating RGB maps. A reference point map was added as well.

4.2. Macroscopically and microscopically

Macroscopically

On the large scale, the dialect divisions obtained were in close agreement with the prevailing theory. In particular, the east-west boundary, which has been the focus of interest in Japanese dialectology, was in agreement in terms of the geographical location of the border.

However, there were discrepancies in the hierarchical structure of the dendrogram which did not show that the Ryukyuan dialects (and Kyushu dialects) are far removed from the mainland dialects. On the other hand, Map 7 shows that the Southern Ryukyuan dialects and the Okinawan dialects are most distant to the dialect of Tokyo. This agrees with previous studies in which the usage rate of standard forms was found to show a neat hierarchy of dialects from different regions in the proximity of Tokyo.

Microscopically

When looking at the data in detail, enclaves were observed. In previous studies that focused on the average use rate of words in the prefectures it was not possible to detect those enclaves.

The enclaves we found may be the result of migration. According to introductory books on dialect in the first half of the 20th century, there were enclaves of feudal lords and their vassals in various parts of Japan. There were regional differences with social stratification due to the relocation of the feudal lords of the Edo shogunate. Thanks to a large-scale study on the (new) dialect formation in mass settlements in Hokkaido, the hypothesis that regional differences fade away after three generations has been

proposed. This tendency seemed applicable to derivational relations. On the other hand, in mountainous areas throughout Japan, there are legends of medieval samurai who were defeated in battle and migrated. In the mountainous areas, there are villages that use a different language from that of the surrounding area. Whether or not the enclaves found in this paper are the result of emigration should be examined on an individual basis in the future.

The individual differences that suggest the existence of enclaves may also be due to mere coincidence. Whether it is a coincidence or not can be determined by comparing our results with the results of an analysis on the basis of other items.

4.2. Future developments

The first data ever treated quantitatively were standard word forms of 82 LAJ items each of them being averaged per prefecture (Inoue 2001). It was conjectured at that time that other items and approaches show similar distribution patterns. With this paper, our earlier desire for a quantitative study of the entire LAJ 2400 localities data has been fulfilled. Although the number of items in this study is small, it agrees well with the previous analysis and demonstrates the reliability of both approaches.

In the previous analysis of the standard word forms for the 82 LAJ items, multivariate analysis was also applied to the word dimension of the data matrix, and succeeded in confirming relationships with the semantic field, frequency of use, and year of first appearance in the literature. This method can also be applied to the 37 items that were used in this study.

The large language difference between mainland Japan and Ryukyu (Okinawa) was striking. The chain of mutual intelligibility was not established in Japan, and the language difference was comparable to that of Germanic languages in northern Europe.

In our study we focused on lexical and phonetic/phonological variation in word forms. But we are aware that measures focusing on morphological, syntactic and prosodic variation may yield different results. Useful future research may be to study these levels as well.

Future quantitative work may also include application to ALE data and other European dialectology data; application to the Swadesh list and parts of Bible, as well as to discourse, which is already underway.

Some quantitative studies have added GIS geographic information to look at the relationship between topography, transportation, economics, and history. These new approaches will allow generalizations to be made about the rules and regularities of dialect distribution in general.

References

- Bolognesi, Roberto and Wilbert Heeringa (2002) De invloed van dominante talen op het lexicon en de fonologie van Sardische dialecten [The influence of dominant languages on the lexicon and phonology of Sardinian dialects]. *Gramma/TTT: tijdschrift voor taalwetenschap* 9(1): 45–84. URI: <http://www.wjheeringa.nl/papers/rom01.pdf>
- Cronbach, Lee J. (1951) Coefficient alpha and the internal structure of tests. *Psychometrika* 16: 297–334. URI: http://cda.psych.uiuc.edu/psychometrika_highly_cited_articles/cronbach_1951.pdf
- Delaunay, Boris (1934) Sur la sphère vide. *Bulletin de l'Académie des Sciences de l'URSS, Classe des Sciences Mathématiques et Naturelles* 6: 793–800. URI: http://galiulin.narod.ru/delaunay_.pdf
- Embleton, Sheila (1993) Multidimensional scaling as a dialectometrical technique: outline of a research project. In: R. Köhler & B. Rieger (eds.), *Contributions to Quantitative Linguistics*, 267–276. Dordrecht: Kluwer.
- Embleton, Sheila, Dorin Uritescu & Eric S. Wheeler (1993) Defining dialect regions with interpretations: advancing the mds approach. *Literary and Linguistic Computing* 28(1): 13–22. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1093/lilc/fqs048>
- Gere, Attila (2023) Recommendations for validating hierarchical clustering in consumer sensory projects. *Current Research in Food Science* 6: 100522. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.crf.2023.100522>
- Goebel, Hans (1981) Eléments d'analyse dialectométrique (avec application à l'ais). *Revue de linguistique romane* 45: 349–420.
- Goebel, Hans (1982) *Dialektometrie; Prinzipien und Methoden des Einsatzes der numerischen Taxonomie im Bereich der Dialektgeographie* [Dialectometry; principles and methods of using numerical taxonomy in the field of dialect geography]. Philosophisch-Historische Klasse Denkschriften 157. Vienna: Verlag der Österreichischen Akademie der Wissenschaften. With assistance of W.-D. Rase and H. Pudlatz.
- Goebel, Hans (1983) Parquet polygonal et treillis triangulaire: les deux versants de la dialectométrie interponctuelle. *Revue de linguistique romane* 47: 353–412.
- Goebel, Hans (2002) Analyse dialectométrique des structures de profondeur de l'ALF. *Revue de linguistique romane* 66(261–262): 5–63.
- Goebel, Hans (2006) Recent advances in Salzburg dialectometry. *Literary and linguistic computing* 21(4): 411–435. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1093/lilc/fql042>
- Goebel, Hans (2007) On the geolinguistic change in Northern France between 1300 and 1900: a dialectometrical inquiry. In: *Proceedings of Ninth Meeting of the ACL Special Interest Group in Computational Morphology and Phonology*, 75–83. URI: <https://aclanthology.org/W07-1310/>
- Goebel, Hans (2010). Dialectometry: Theoretical prerequisites, practical problems, and concrete applications (mainly with examples draw from the "Atlas linguistique de la France", 1902-1910). *Dialectologia: revista electrònica* 63–77. URI: <https://raco.cat/index.php/Dialectologia/article/view/242102/324714>
- Grosse, Rudolf (1955) *Die meissnische Sprachlandschaft: Dialektgeographische Untersuchungen zur obersächsischen Sprach- und Siedlungsgeschichte*. Halle: M. Niemeyer.
- Heeringa, Wilbert (2004) Measuring Dialect Pronunciation Differences using Levenshtein Distance. Unpublished doctoral dissertation, University of Groningen. URI: <http://www.wjheeringa.nl/thesis/>
- Heeringa, Wilbert, John Nerbonne and Peter Kleiweg (2010) Dialectvariatie, dialectafstanden en dialectindelingen. Een formele analyse van uitspraakverschillen [Dialect variation, dialect distances and dialect divisions. A formal analysis of pronunciation differences]. In: Onno Boonstra and Anton Schuurman (eds.), *Tijd en ruimte. Nieuwe toepassingen van GIS in de alfawetenschappen*, 88–101. Utrecht: Uitgeverij Matrijs.

- Huisman, John L.A., Asifa Majid and Roeland van Hout, R. (2019) The geographical configuration of a language area influences linguistic diversity. *PLoS ONE* 14(6): e0217363. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0217363>
- Huisman, John L.A. (2021) Variation in form and meaning across the Japonic language family: With a focus on the Ryukyuan languages. Doctoral dissertation, Radboud University Nijmegen. URI: https://pure.mpg.de/rest/items/item_3311139/component/file_3311141/content
- Inoue, Fumio (1996) Computational dialectology (1). *Area and Culture Studies* 52: 67–102. doi: <https://doi.org/10.15026/23628>
- Inoue, Fumio (2001) *Keiryoteki Hogen Kukaku* [Quantificational Dialect Classification] Tokyo: Meiji Shoin.
- Inoue, Fumio (2020) Standard language distribution in LAJ and railway distance --- Geographical and historical interpretation of limestone cave model. *Dialectologia: revista electrónica* 24: 111–156. URI: <http://www.publicacions.ub.edu/revistes/dialectologia24/documentos/1602.pdf>
- Inoue, Fumio & Yasuo Yoshioka (eds.) (2003) *Kyushu no Hogen*. Tokyo: Yumani Shobo.
- Ivić, Pavle (1962) On the structure of dialectal differentiation. *Word* 18(1–3): 33–53. URI: <https://doi.org/10.1080/00437956.1962.11659764>
- Jain, Anil K. and Richard C. Dubes (1988) *Algorithms for Clustering Data*. Englewood Cliffs, New Jersey: Prentice Hall.
- Johnson, Stephen C. (1967) Hierarchical clustering schemes. *Psychometrika* 32: 241–254. URI: http://cda.psych.uiuc.edu/psychometrika_highly_cited_articles/johnson_1967.pdf
- Kawaguchi, Yuji and Fumio Inoue (2002) Japanese dialectology in historical perspectives. *Revue belge de Philologie et d'Histoire* 80(3): 801–829. doi: <https://doi.org/10.3406/rbph.2002.4642>
- Kessler, Brett (1995) Computational dialectology in Irish Gaelic. In: *Proceedings of the 7th Conference of the European Chapter of the Association for Computational Linguistics*, 60–67. Dublin: EACL. URI: <https://arxiv.org/pdf/cmp-1g/9503002.pdf>
- King, Benjamin (1967) Step-wise clustering procedures. *Journal of the American Statistical Association* 69: 86–101. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1080/01621459.1967.10482890>
- Kokuritsu Kokugo Kenkyujo (NLRI) (1966) *Nihon gengo chizu kaisetsu: Hôhō* [Introduction to the linguistic atlas of Japan: Methodology]. In: Kokuritsu Kokugo Kenkyujo (NLRI) (ed.), *Nihon gengo chizu* (Linguistic atlas of Japan). Tokyo: Printing bureau, Ministry of Finance.
- Krijthe, Jesse (2015) *Rtsne: T-Distributed Stochastic Neighbor Embedding using a Barnes-Hut Implementation*. <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/Rtsne/>. R package version 0.13.
- Kruskal, Joseph. B. and Myron Wish (1978) *Multidimensional Scaling*. Sage University Paper Series on Quantitative Applications in the Social Sciences 07–011. Newbury Park: Sage Publications.
- Kumagai, Yasuo (ed.) (2013a) *Daikibo hôgen dêta no takakuteki bunseki seika hôkokusho: Gengo chizu to hôgen danwa shiryô* [Analyzing large-scale dialectal survey data from multiple perspectives]. Tokyo: Kokuritsu Kokugo Kenkyujo (NINJAL).
- Kumagai, Yasuo (2013b) Development of a way to visualize and observe linguistic similarities on a linguistic atlas. *Working papers from NWAV Asia-Pacific* 2. URI: <https://www2.ninjal.ac.jp/past-events/nwavap02/Kumagai-NWAVAP2-2013.pdf>
- Kumagai, Yasuo (2016) Developing the Linguistic Atlas of Japan Database and advancing analysis of geographical distributions of dialects. In: Marie-Hélène Côté, Remco Knooihuizen, John Nerbonne (eds.), *The Future of Dialects. Selected Papers from Methods in Dialectology XV*, 333–362. doi: <https://doi.org/10.17169/langsci.b81.159>
- Matthews, Peter Hugoe (1997) *The Concise Oxford Dictionary of Linguistics*. Oxford Paperback Reference. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Nakamoto Masachie (1983) *Ryukyu goishi no kenkyu* [Study on Ryukyuan lexicological history] Tokyo: San'ichi shobo

- Nerbonne, John and Wilbert Heeringa (1998) Computationale vergelijking en classificatie van dialecten [Computational comparison and classification of dialects]. *Taal en Tongval, Tijdschrift voor Dialectologie* 50(2): 164–193. URI: <https://www.let.rug.nl/~nerbonne/papers/tetv99.pdf>
- Nerbonne, John, Wilbert Heeringa and Peter Kleiweg (1999) Edit distance and dialect proximity. In David Sankoff and Joseph B. Kruskal (eds.), *Time Warps, String Edits, and Macromolecules. The Theory and Practice of Sequence Comparison*, 2nd, v–xv. Stanford: CSLI.
- Nunnally, Jum C. and Ira H. Bernstein (1994) *Psychometric theory* (3rd ed.). McGraw-Hill.
- Onishi, Takuichiro (2002). Dialect research at the National Institute for the Japanese Language. *Dialectologia et Geolinguistica (DiG)* 10: 87–96. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1515/dig.2002.2002.10.87>
Also available at: <https://www2.ninjal.ac.jp/takoni/English/DRNIJLA.pdf>
- Séguy, Jean (1973) La dialectométrie dans l'Atlas linguistique de la Gascogne. *Revue de linguistique romane* 37: 1–24.
- Togerson, Warren S. (1952) Multidimensional scaling: I. Theory and method. *Psychometrika* 17(4): 401–419. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02288916> Also available at: <http://www.galileoco.com/literature/torgerson52.pdf>
- Swadesh Morris (1952) Lexico-Statistic Dating of Prehistoric Ethnic Contacts: With Special Reference to North American Indians and Eskimos. *Proceedings of the American Philosophical Society* 96(4): 452–463. URI: <https://www.jstor.org/stable/3143802>
- van der Maaten, Laurens (2014) Accelerating t-SNE using Tree-Based Algorithms. *Journal of Machine Learning Research* 15(93): 3221–3245. URI: <https://jmlr.org/papers/v15/vandermaaten14a.html>
- van der Maaten, Laurens and Geoffrey Hinton (2008) Visualizing Data Using t-SNE. *Journal of Machine Learning Research* 9(86): 2579–2605. URI: <https://www.jmlr.org/papers/v9/vandermaaten08a.html>
- Ward Jr, Joe H. (1963) Hierarchical grouping to optimize an objective function. *Journal of the American Statistical Association* 58: 236–244. doi: <https://doi.org/10.2307/2282967>
- Wieling, Martijn, Jelena Prokić and John Nerbonne, J. (2009) Evaluating the pairwise alignment of pronunciations. In: Borin, L. and Lendvai, P., editors, *Proceedings of the EACL 2009 Workshop on Language Technology and Resources for Cultural Heritage, Social Sciences, Humanities, and Education, (LaTeCH - SHELTeR 2009). Workshop at the 12th Meeting of the European Chapter of the Association for Computational Linguistics. Athens, 30 March 2009*, 26–34. URI: <https://aclanthology.org/W09-0304.pdf>
- Wieling, Martijn (2012) A quantitative approach to social and geographical dialect variation. Doctoral dissertation, University of Groningen. URI: <https://hdl.handle.net/11370/cd637817-572f-4826-98c1-08272775fb64>
- Yanagita, Kunio (1943) *Kagyu Ko* [Reflections on Snail] Tokyo: Sogensha
- Yarimizu, Kanetaka (2007) Hogen bunpo zenkoku chizu ni okeru kyotsugoka no jokyo [The situation of common language in GAJ]. *Nihongogaku* 26 (11): 112–119.

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